

A Novel Neural Network Approach to Proactive 3-D Beamforming

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Abstract—This study explores three-dimensional proactive beamforming at millimeter wave frequencies using transformer neural networks (TNNs), long short-term memory networks (LSTMs) and gated-recurrent units (GRUs). The proposed scheme aims to reduce beamforming latency by predicting future directions of arrival (DoAs) based on past observations, allowing the system to prepare beamforming weights proactively. We simulate an urban environment using OpenStreetMap data to generate realistic movement paths, creating a comprehensive dataset for training and evaluation. Our focus is on the predictive capacity of TNNs, LSTMs and GRUs to anticipate future DoAs, even in non-line-of-sight scenarios influenced by urban infrastructure. We detail the environment simulation setup, the ray-tracing mechanism as well as the movement generation process for pedestrians and vehicles. A statistical analysis on the prediction accuracy and response time is presented to assess the most accurate model and discuss the trade-offs between the architectures. In addition, an end-to-end AI-based proactive beamforming scenario is examined where zero-forcing is applied on moving users. This is to further demonstrate and evaluate the capabilities and the performance of each model. Our findings suggest that proactive beamforming can significantly enhance performance in dynamically changing urban landscapes, offering a promising avenue for future research and development in adaptive communication systems.

Index Terms—adaptive beamforming, transformer, recurrent neural networks, proactive beamforming, direction of arrival estimation

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the evolving landscape of wireless communications, the demand for higher data rates and improved quality of service necessitates the development of sophisticated beamforming techniques. Beamforming, a signal processing technique used by antenna arrays to direct the transmission or reception of signals in specific directions, has been fundamental in enhancing communication efficiency and signal quality. Traditional beamforming approaches, employed for adaptive beamforming, have significantly contributed to the advancement of wireless communications by optimizing the antenna pattern in

response to the signal environment. However, the dynamic and complex nature of urban communication scenarios, especially at millimeter wave (mmWave) frequencies, presents challenges that exceed the capabilities of conventional methods.

Adaptive beamforming is the process of dynamically adjusting the pattern of the antenna array to focus its energy in desired directions (i.e., signals of interest or SoIs) while suppressing interference (i.e., signals of avoidance or SoAs) and noise. In order to achieve this, a beamforming mechanism receives information regarding the incoming signals and adjusts the radiation pattern of the antenna according to a preferred beamforming strategy. Typically, the output of beamforming algorithms is a weight vector which describes the feeding current distribution (amplitude and phase) across the elements of the antenna array. It is the task of the beamforming algorithm to configure these currents in order to achieve the optimal radiation pattern for each scenario. Various approaches have been proposed to construct this weight vector from the incoming signal information [1]. Some methods directly map the received signal data (i.e., spatial signal profile, covariance matrix of received signals) to the weight vector [2], [3]. This method is highly efficient in environments where channel characteristics are relatively stable or can be accurately predicted, allowing for a straightforward optimization of the beam path towards the intended users while minimizing interference.

In contrast, others partition the beamforming operation into two distinct phases: estimating the direction of arrival (DoA) of the incoming signals and subsequently generating the weight vector based on this estimation [4], [5], [6], [7]. In our study, we consider the second approach for its enhanced accuracy and adaptability in dynamically changing environments or scenarios with complex interference patterns. Conventional deterministic algorithms such as the Minimum-Variance Distortionless Response (MVDR) [8], the null-steering Beamformer (NSB) [9] and others [1] have demonstrated impeccable accuracy in weight production and radiation pattern formation. However, the complexity of their mathematical operations results in slower processing speeds, rendering them less suitable for the demands of future wireless networks. To negate such disadvantages, advancements in computational efficiency and complexity are needed, allowing for real-time DoA estimation and weight vector adjustment without incurring significant delays or computational overhead. While recent advancements in 3D beamforming, such as the use of planar true-time-delay (TTD) networks for wideband analog beamforming [10] and adaptive beamforming strategies for phased array radio telescopes [11], focus on improving signal control in static

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scenarios, our work targets proactive DoA prediction to reduce beamforming latency in dynamic, fast-changing environments.

Artificial intelligence (AI) and more specifically machine learning, has already revolutionized the field of wireless communications offering promising avenues to address such challenges. Particularly, deep neural networks (NNs), known for their exceptional ability to perform non-linear, highly complex operations, have opened new possibilities in adaptive beamforming [12], [13]. So far, there are several works demonstrating the capabilities of NNs both on the task of DoA estimation [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20] and weight production [21], [22]. While other approaches, such as the graph NN (GNN)-based method for sum-rate maximization in multi-user multiple-input-single-output networks [23] and the graph-attention based approach for energy-efficient beamforming [24], focus on optimizing transmission efficiency and energy consumption, respectively, our work targets latency reduction through proactive DoA prediction, making it more suitable for environments with fast-moving users. On the other hand, recent advancements in enhancing non-line-of-sight (NLoS) coverage include the use of AI-enhanced passive EM skins, which improve signal reflection and coverage in static environments through the design of smart electromagnetic surfaces [25]. While these solutions enhance signal reliability in large-scale, low-power deployments, our approach focuses on leveraging multi-path propagation and historical data to increase coverage without the need for additional equipment deployment. Considering the progress in this field, the two-part approach of DoA estimation followed by weight production can potentially be covered by an end-to-end NN-based system which will drastically improve the response time of the overall process. However, advancements in the area of *proactive beamforming* suggest that this approach could be enhanced even further.

Proactive beamforming (also mentioned as *predictive beamforming* in the literature) is a recent contribution to the field of adaptive beamforming aiming to predict the future trajectory of a moving user in order to proactively perform the beamforming operation. Unlike traditional beamforming methods that react to current signal conditions, proactive beamforming anticipates future signal environments, enabling more predictive adjustments to the beam pattern. This approach is especially beneficial in urban scenarios where the signal environment rapidly changes due to the movement of users and vehicular traffic. Most applications in literature focus on the vehicle to infrastructure (V2I) communication where radio links demand exact alignment between the narrow beams which typically requires excessive signaling overhead. Most of these works rely on the use of roadside units (RSU) which conventionally scans the angular interval of interest and pairs the transmit and receive beams with the strongest channel gain. However, for vehicular applications with dynamic network topology and environments, beam pairing has to be done frequently, leading to exceedingly high communication cost [26]. Integrated sensing [27], [28] and multi-modal NN-based models [29] are also proposed to accurately predict the trajectories of moving vehicles from the perspective of RSUs. In addition, there are a number of works that adopt Kalman filters and simple

kinematic models to track the motion of moving vehicles [30], [31] and minimize tracking error. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the concept of proactive beamforming has not yet been applied for both pedestrian and vehicle user movement in an urban scenario.

The key challenge at higher frequency communications is the significant path loss, where signal strength degrades rapidly over distance due to the shorter wavelengths [32]. This limits coverage and makes traditional passive beamforming techniques insufficient for dynamic environments like urban areas, where obstructions and fast-moving users further compound signal degradation. Advanced techniques such as proactive adaptive beamforming can circumvent the rigidity of fixed beamforming techniques having more flexibility both in terms of angle coverage space and adaptation to the changing environment. Having a system that takes advantage of multi-path propagation to increase coverage is vital in higher frequency communications where increased path loss greatly reduces line-of-sight (LoS) connections.

Transformer neural networks (TNNs) are currently leading the domain of natural language processing (NLP) due to their exceptional ability to handle sequential data, understand context, and generate coherent and relevant responses [33]. Their architecture, characterized by self-attention mechanisms, allows for the analysis of inputs in their entirety, enabling the model to weigh the significance of different parts of the data relative to each other. TNNs have already showcased their versatility beyond the realm of NLP, branching out into diverse areas such as movement prediction [34], [35], [36], [37], [38]. This expansion highlights the adaptability of TNNs to various domains, where their capability to analyze and predict complex patterns offers innovative solutions to longstanding challenges. In pedestrian trajectory prediction, TNNs demonstrated their ability to surpass the previously established recurrent NN (RNN) models which lead the research on this field [39], [40]. The self-attention mechanism in TNNs is their defining advantage over the sequential step-by-step processing of RNNs. This innovative feature allows TNNs to provide enhanced context for each input by comprehensively understanding its relationship to all other elements in the sequence, while simultaneously preserving the integral sequential nature of the data. In [34] a TNN and a bidirectional transformer (BERT) is used to forecast the future trajectories of individual people using the (x,y) coordinates of their previous motion. Evaluated on the different trajectory datasets, TNNs outperform the conventional long-short-term memory (LSTMs) units which renders them a better alternative for movement forecasting. Another TNN-based pedestrian movement prediction model is presented in [35] using an encoder-decoder architecture which forecast multiple future trajectories of moving pedestrians, assigning a probability to each of these trajectories. In [36] a joint TNN is proposed to predict trajectories and make behavioral decisions regarding the movement of pedestrians simultaneously. The authors of [37] propose a graph TNN for trajectory prediction purposed for autonomous driving. Another spatio-temporal graph-transformer is shown in [38] to predict future trajectories of multiple traffic agents. The supremacy of TNN-based models over the RNN-based ar-

Fig. 1. With proactive 3-D beamforming, we predict the future DoAs of both desired and undesired users to generate the appropriate weight vector before the next timestep, thereby reducing overall response time. Beam-steering and zero-forcing are performed by adjusting both the azimuth and elevation angles.

chitecture is also demonstrated here both in accuracy and response time. Nevertheless, we should not disregard the use of LSTMs, with their established performance in time-series forecasting and sequential processing [41], [42]. In addition, we include the gated recurrent unit (GRU) based RNN into the comparison [43]. When compared with LSTMs, GRUs have demonstrated similar performance with a reduced overall response time [21], [44].

This work is motivated by the promising performance of TNNs and LSTMs in trajectory prediction, as well as studies on minimizing tracking errors in vehicle scenarios. Our goal is to explore the potential of deep learning models for user-agnostic DoA prediction, leveraging insightful data to enhance the pattern recognition capabilities of these models.

This manuscript introduces an innovative approach to proactive beamforming, utilizing TNNs, LSTMs and GRUs to predict the future DoA of incoming signals in an urban setting. By leveraging the historical sequence of DoAs at current timestep t , our models predict the next DoA at $t + 1$ both for SoI and SoAs (as demonstrated in Fig. 1), allowing for the antenna system to preemptively adjust its beam pattern prior to subsequent timesteps. This has an immediate impact on user experience by minimizing beamforming temporal overhead while effectively leveraging multi-path propagation. This reduces connection drops and increases reliability in challenging environments. This method stands in contrast to both conventional beamforming and existing predictive beamforming techniques, which predominantly rely on static environmental models or simple LoS movement predictions. Our approach is particularly tailored for high-frequency operations, such as the 27 GHz mmWave band, which is crucial for next-generation wireless communication systems but is characterized by significant propagation challenges. The key feature of this work

is its dual focus on proactive DoA prediction and adaptive beamforming, surpassing traditional trajectory prediction. Our model dynamically adjusts to changing propagation conditions, like LoS and NLoS, while optimizing beamforming in real time — an aspect usually overlooked by conventional methods. We simulate an urban environment using OpenStreetMap data [45], to mimic realistic urban propagation conditions. Pedestrian movement paths are generated through a novel technique that creates randomized walks based on predefined tracks, thereby enriching the dataset with a wide range of DoA scenarios both in LoS and NLoS conditions. This comprehensive simulation environment allows us to train the NN models effectively, demonstrating the potential of our method to improve beamforming predictions in dynamically changing urban landscapes. The novelty of this research lies not only in predicting DoAs at future timesteps but also in identifying the parameters and model architecture that can adapt its predictions based on both the user’s dynamic mobility patterns and the unique signal propagation characteristics of each electromagnetic environment. By focusing on this dual adaptation, our approach aims to utilize as much environmental information as possible and leverage multi-path propagation to increase coverage.

The contribution of this work can be summarized as follows:

- *Pedestrian and vehicle movement production.* We propose a novel method to generate artificial datasets of moving users in an urban scenario.
- *End-to-end AI-based proactive beamforming scheme.* Both DoA prediction and beamforming weight production are performed by pre-trained NNs. The final system is able to perform zero-forcing 3-D beamforming by predicting the DoAs of both desired and undesired users and produce the optimal radiation pattern, solely with the use of NNs.
- *DoA predictor based on an encoder-only transformer architecture.* We propose a TNN model which is able to predict the future DoA of a user given the history of previously received DoAs. The size of the input sequence can be dynamic.
- *Performance comparison and statistical analysis.* We provide a statistical analysis to compare the proposed TNN model with LSTM-based and GRU-based RNN models and present the advantages and trade-offs for selecting the TNN model. We additionally implement a Kalman Filter, offering a non-NN benchmark for comparing the performance of our proposed models. The performance of each model is also demonstrated on a random beamforming scenario with moving users.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II provides a detailed definition of the problem and the setup of our simulation environment, including the configurations for the receiver and the methodology for simulating movement. Section III describes the dataset preparation process, including the generation of synthetic data and the normalization techniques applied. Section IV outlines the Kalman Filter implementation, while Section V shows the architecture and implementation details of the TNN, LSTM and GRU-based

RNNs used for DoA prediction. Section VI presents the results of our experiments, including a comparative analysis on the time complexity, the performance of each model, and the application of the proposed proactive beamforming scheme in a real-world scenario, illustrating its potential benefits. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper, summarizing our findings and suggesting directions for future research.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION AND SETUP

A. Problem Definition

Consider t_s to be the time interval at which DoA estimation is performed, and t_{DoA} as the time required for a selected DoA estimation algorithm to execute. Following the extraction of DoAs, a beamforming weight vector \mathbf{W} must be computed. This can be achieved using either a conventional algorithm (MVDR, NSB), or through an NN-based beamformer (as the one proposed in [22]). This computation extends the temporal delay of the overall process by t_{BF} . Our proposed scheme introduces an additional component that predicts the future DoA DoA_{pred} at a temporal cost of t_{pred} , before the next preordained DoA estimation is executed at time $2t_s$. This way, the optimal future weight vector \mathbf{W}_{2t_s} is intended to be prepared proactively, before the subsequent DoA estimation takes place. When the next DoA estimation is executed at $2t_s$, the real DoA (DoA_{real}) is extracted. By comparing the predicted with the real value and according to a certain tolerance ε on the prediction error, the system decides either to use the proactively created weight vector or to proceed with the regular beamforming process. The entire process is illustrated in Fig. 2. Our ultimate goal is to minimize the frequency of DoA estimations during the adaptive beamforming process, allowing them to be performed at larger intervals as a "sanity check" for the DoA predictor. However, achieving this depends significantly on the confidence in our predictive model's accuracy. At this stage, we primarily focus on reducing the time required for weight production following the second DoA estimation at $2t_s$. Thus, our target is to satisfy

$$t_{\text{pred}} + t_{\text{BF}} \leq t_s. \quad (1)$$

The above expression ensures that the time to predict the DoA and generate beamforming weights is less than the interval between successive DoA estimations, allowing the system to update proactively. The required update rate, t_s , depends on the scenario, ranging from 100-500 Hz for fast-moving users to 10-50 Hz for slower ones. Thus, (1) serves either as a constraint or a condition for the maximum DoA update rate that the proposed scheme can support.

To better define the problem mathematically, let the state of each user at time t be represented by the vector:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = [\phi_t, \theta_t], \quad (2)$$

where ϕ_t, θ_t denote the azimuth and elevation DoA angles at timestep t . The primary objective is to predict the future state \mathbf{x}_{t+t_s} based on past observations up to time t . This can be expressed as:

$$\hat{\phi}_{t+t_s}, \hat{\theta}_{t+t_s} = f(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{x}_{t-t_s}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{t-kt_s}) + \varepsilon, \quad (3)$$

where f represents the predictive model (Kalman Filter, TNN, LSTM, or GRU), and ε accounts for the prediction error. The predicted DoA is then used to compute the beamforming weight vector \mathbf{w}_{t+t_s} for the next time step, allowing the system to proactively adjust the beamforming direction based on the predicted user trajectory.

Fig. 2. Proactive beamforming scheme. By predicting the future DoA, the weights are prepared proactively at an earlier sampling timestep.

To define the design goals of the predictive model, we balance accuracy and temporal response. Meeting constraint (1) is crucial, as it is tied to the DoA update rate, which depends on factors like user speed, carrier frequency, and beamwidth. Once this is met, the focus shifts to accuracy, expressed by the tolerance level ε . Larger antennas with narrower half-power beamwidths (HPBW) reduce ε , leaving less room for error. For instance, an 8×8 UPA at 27 GHz has an approximate HPBW of 12.7 degrees at broadside [46], narrowing to 3.4 degrees with a 30×30 UPA. The goal is to minimize prediction errors well below the HPBW, as even small improvements can significantly enhance beamforming performance, especially in dynamic environments. Thus, if two models satisfy constraint (1) and show similar levels of accuracy, we prioritize the model with the lower prediction error.

B. Simulation Environment Setup

In this study, we address the complex challenge of predicting future DoAs for mobile users within an urban setting. This task is complicated by intricate urban layouts and unpredictable signal propagation, particularly under NLoS conditions. Early in our research, we establish the assumption that pedestrian movements, are more predictable in urban settings due to the predetermined paths dictated by city planning. Global positioning system (GPS) tracks of pedestrians reveal that despite its random nature, human movement in a city is directed and ordained by the sidewalks, crosswalks and

Fig. 3. Heatmap of recorded activities classified as "walk" over a selected area near the port of Piraeus in Athens, Greece. Heatmap taken using the Heatmap Strava tool. <https://www.strava.com/maps/global-heatmap>.

generally the urban landscape. This can be further validated by observing heatmaps of GPS traces of pedestrians over an urban area as Fig. 3 illustrates. The electromagnetic equivalent of these movement patterns would be the DoA trajectories of the transmitting devices carried by the moving users which attempt to link with the nearest base station. Similar to GPS traces, DoA trajectories can reveal the main arteries of signal propagation in a busy area, which is the basis for our proactive beamforming scheme.

The significance of the proposed scheme comes from leveraging these movement patterns to save computational time during beamforming. Despite the difficulty of modeling such complex and non-linear patterns, such applications are enabled by deep learning methods [39] which have already demonstrated unprecedented predictive capabilities in more improbable tasks [36]. In our work, we attempt to test whether NNs can effectively correlate historical DoA records with future signal directions. A critical factor in training NNs under a supervised learning scheme is the availability of substantial data. Possessing a large dataset is crucial for training accurate and robust models, and in our case, it could unveil the capabilities of a model tasked with a previously untested challenge. A major obstacle however, is the scarcity of real-world data on recorded DoA trajectories from multiple users to a single base station. To the best of the authors' knowledge, and as of the time this study is conducted, no such dataset is publicly available from a credible source. Nevertheless, the ability to simulate a wireless electromagnetic urban environment using dedicated software presents a viable alternative. This capability allows for the potential use of real-world GPS tracks. Regrettably, the challenge extends to finding open-source, location-specific GPS trace data for moving users, including pedestrians and vehicles. Currently, there is no publicly available dataset that provides extensive user tracks. Notably, there exist several open-source datasets aimed for trajectory prediction. TrajNet [47] is a dataset containing records of surveillance cameras with varying crowd densities and complex trajectory patterns. Datasets like ETH [48] and UCY [49] also contain records of pedestrians in busy scenarios from a birds eye view. Such image-based datasets are intended for computer-vision tasks

Fig. 4. Left: Photograph taken in Piraeus, Athens, Greece. Retrieved from <http://dimand.gr/en/projects/piraeus-tower/>. Right: The same area simulated with the MATLAB Site Viewer tool using data from [45].

where predicting future movement is based on identifying and forecasting the trajectory of a moving pedestrian using a sequence of images. The trajectories of these datasets do not include geographical coordinate information for each moving pedestrian and the coverage area is limited to the field of view of the camera. This makes it difficult to incorporate such data into electromagnetic environment simulations. This scarcity of data necessitates innovative approaches to data generation and utilization within our research framework.

For this reason, it is required that we generate synthetic data in order to continue this study. To pursue a more realistic and location-specific approach, we simulate movement patterns based on the structural pathways dictated by urban environments, such as sidewalks for pedestrians and roads for vehicles. These simulations aim to reflect a spectrum of plausible urban movement patterns, albeit without the granularity of specific real-world trajectories. Nevertheless, our ultimate objective is to assess the viability of employing NNs to improve beamforming techniques, not movement prediction. This exploration is driven by a need to understand the potential of these models to predict future signal directions, contributing to the development of more adaptive and efficient communication systems in complex environments. Thus, we deem the simulated movement approach sufficient for the purposes of this research.

We decided to work on a selected area around the port of Piraeus, in Athens, Greece as shown in Fig. 3. Even though any given urban area could be considered for our implementation, an important advantage of the selected scene is the tower of Piraeus, a tall building (shown in Fig. 4) upon which we can place the base station in order to cover as much of the urban area that lies underneath. The ability to cover a bigger area comes with the advantage of having a large space at which the simulated users can move in, which in turn helps us generate a large and diverse dataset. The OpenStreetMap [45] file of this area is imported in MATLAB [50] using the Site Viewer tool [51] as shown in Fig. 4.

C. Receiver Configuration

For the base station, we use a uniform planar array (UPA) of an 8×8 configuration. The element spacing is $d = \frac{\lambda}{2}$ where λ is the wavelength of the operating frequency. In our setup, we consider the operating frequency to be $f = 27\text{GHz}$ bringing us to mmWave communications. The base station, in receiver

Fig. 5. Tests with different antenna tilt. The red mark symbolizes the location of the base station. a) [Zenith, Azimuth] tilt: $[0^\circ, 0^\circ]$ b) [Zenith, Azimuth] tilt: $[-10^\circ, -20^\circ]$ c) [Zenith, Azimuth] tilt: $[-15^\circ, -20^\circ]$ d) [Zenith, Azimuth] tilt: $[-20^\circ, -20^\circ]$

Fig. 6. Left: The predefined pedestrian paths in the coverage area. Right: The predefined road paths in the coverage area. Drawn using the GPS Visualizer tool [52].

mode, is placed on top of the tower with an additional height of 3 meters. In order to configure the tilt of the planar array, we examined different configurations in both zenith and azimuth tilt. As shown in Fig. 5, tilting the transmitter by -20° and -20° from its initial zenith and azimuth orientation respectively, yields better coverage over the urban area we are interested in. The coverage area is calculated considering a transmitting power of 5 W. For the transmitter antennas of the users, we assume the simplistic scenario of isotropic point sources, to reduce the computational cost of each simulation.

D. Simulation of Movement

To generate movement tracks on this map, we first need to specify the geographical coordinates where users are likely to move. Using the coverage map shown in Fig. 5d as a reference,

we meticulously draw the predefined paths of sidewalks and roads using the GPS Visualizer online tool [52]. Specifically, we design designated paths for pedestrians along the main axes of sidewalks and crosswalks, and we also incorporate random walk patterns in larger areas such as parks and squares. For vehicles, we stick to the main designated roads that lie within the coverage area. The motion dynamics will be later dictated by the following proposed method, making these paths merely a geographical indicator for the users to move. Each predefined path $P(k)$, ($k = 0, 1, \dots, K$, where $K + 1$ is the total number of traces in the path) is defined by a set of geographical coordinates. The order of these coordinates indicates the direction of movement. We consider the pedestrian paths to be bi-directional which is not the case for road paths. We define 4 types of activity for pedestrians and each activity comes with a specific velocity range, as also described in [53]. Thus, the velocity range in (m/s) is given by the following:

$$A_i(\text{activity}) = \begin{cases} [0.6, 0.8] & \text{if activity} = \text{"stroll"} \\ [0.8, 1.5] & \text{if activity} = \text{"walk"} \\ [1.5, 4] & \text{if activity} = \text{"jog"} \\ [4.0, 10.0] & \text{if activity} = \text{"run"} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where i indexes the user, A_i represents the activity type of the i -th user, and $\bar{v}_i \in A_i$ denotes the average velocity assigned to user i within the range specified by A_i . For vehicles, we define the velocity range to be $[2.7, 13.8]$.

An important clarification must be made regarding our calculations with geographical coordinates. When dealing with points on the Earth's surface represented by latitude and longitude where the distance between the points is relatively small (such as less than 500 meters), the curvature of the Earth can often be reasonably approximated by a flat plane for most practical purposes. This simplifies calculations, allowing us to use linear interpolation and other geometric methods with a negligible precision error.

Next, we start by generating a new track $T_i(m)$, where $m \in \mathbb{Z}$ denotes the trace number. The starting point for a new track $T_i(0)$, is selected as a linear interpolation between two random consecutive traces of the predefined path as shown in Fig. 7. Thus, if $P(k)$ and $P(k+1)$ are these consecutive path traces, the starting point is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} T_i(0)^{\text{Lat}} &= P(k)^{\text{Lat}} + r(P(k+1)^{\text{Lat}} - P(k)^{\text{Lat}}) \\ T_i(0)^{\text{Lon}} &= P(k)^{\text{Lon}} + r(P(k+1)^{\text{Lon}} - P(k)^{\text{Lon}}) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $r \in [0, 1]$ is the random factor, $(T_i(0)^{\text{Lat}}, T_i(0)^{\text{Lon}})$ are the latitude and longitude coordinates of the starting point and $(P(k)^{\text{Lat}}, P(k)^{\text{Lon}}), (P(k+1)^{\text{Lat}}, P(k+1)^{\text{Lon}})$ are the respective coordinates of points $P(k)$ and $P(k+1)$.

To generate the next trace, we need to have a "target" location towards which the user intends to move. The moving user is always located between two traces of the predefined path, the *previous* trace $P(k)$ and the *target* trace $P(k+1)$. As Fig. 7 illustrates, the index for the *target* trace is increased once the distance of the user from the *previous* trace is larger

Fig. 7. The process of creating a new track based on a predefined path. The target trace is updated when the generated new track location exceeds the radius between previous and current target trace.

than the distance of that *previous* trace and the *target* trace. To increase the randomness of pedestrian trajectories, make the walks more realistic and diversify the dataset, we introduce some direction entropy to the movement. More specifically, at each iteration, the bearing pointing towards the target trace is shifted according to an entropy angle θ_E . This angle is randomly assigned according to a normal distribution within a specific maximum angular deviation range, which varies for each activity type.

$$\Delta\theta_{\max_i}(\text{activity}) = \begin{cases} [-40^\circ, 40^\circ] & \text{if activity} = \text{"stroll"} \\ [-30^\circ, 30^\circ] & \text{if activity} = \text{"walk"} \\ [-20^\circ, 20^\circ] & \text{if activity} = \text{"jog"} \\ [-10^\circ, 10^\circ] & \text{if activity} = \text{"run"} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

At each new track step, the entropy angle takes a random value within the maximum angular deviation sector assigned for the i -th user based on their activity ($\theta_{E_i} \in \Delta\theta_{\max_i}$). To calculate the bearing from the current position $T_i(m)$ of the new track to the target trace $P(k+1)$, we use the arctangent function of the two variables y_i and x_i . The first variable y_i , represents the 'east-west' component of the direction with east being positive. It is calculated using the difference in longitude between the position of the i -th user at the m -th iteration $T_i(m)$, and target trace $P(k+1)$ and the cosine of the latitude of $P(k+1)$, effectively projecting it onto the equator in order to find the east-west component relative to the $T_i(m)$. The 'north-south' component x_i combines the northward stretch towards $P(k+1)$ and the correction for the east-west stretching of $P(k+1)$ due to its longitude difference with the $T_i(m)$. Thus the bearing is calculated as:

$$\text{bearing} = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{y_i}{x_i}\right) \quad (7)$$

where:

$$y_i = \sin(P(k+1)^{\text{Lon}} - T_i(m)^{\text{Lon}}) \cos(P(k+1)^{\text{Lat}}) \quad (8)$$

and

$$x_i = \cos(T_i(m)^{\text{Lat}}) \sin(P(k+1)^{\text{Lat}}) - \sin(T_i(m)^{\text{Lat}}) \cos(P(k+1)^{\text{Lat}}) \cos(P(k+1)^{\text{Lon}} - T_i(m)^{\text{Lon}}) \quad (9)$$

Taking into consideration the direction entropy $\theta_{E_i} \in \Delta\theta_{\max_i}$ and (7), the direction of the i -th user at iteration m becomes:

$$b_i(m) = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{y_i}{x_i}\right) + \theta_{E_i} \quad (10)$$

Besides direction, the new track trace location is calculated based on the speed and a turning indication factor the user has at each step. As turning indication we define the proximity of a user to a turn. This is measured by an angle of approach θ_t , which is the angle between the points $T_i(m)$, $P_i(k+1)$ and $P_i(k+2)$ calculated using the cosine rule. Let us take the example of Fig. 8. If $T_i(m)$ is $T1$, $P(k+1)$ is $P2$ and $P(k+2)$ is $P3$, then using the cosine rule, $\theta_t(m)$ can be calculated as:

$$\theta_t(m) = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{|T1P2|^2 + |T1P3|^2 - |P2P3|^2}{2|P2P3|}\right) \quad (11)$$

The angle of approach increases as the user nears the turn, while it is also directly proportional to the turn's steepness. We consider that when users approximate a turn on the predefined path (e.g. pedestrians reaching a corner of a building, vehicles taking a turn towards another street), their velocity is decreased. For the purposes of this study, velocity should reduce to zero for a turn of 180° . Thus, the velocity of the i -th user at step m becomes:

$$|v_i(m)| = \bar{v}_i \left(\frac{180^\circ - |\theta_t(m)|}{180^\circ}\right)^{d_R} \quad (12)$$

where d_R is a deceleration rate which regulates the impact of a turn to the velocity reduction. For pedestrians we set $d_R = 1$ and for vehicles $d_R = 2$ as vehicles are required to decrease their velocity more significantly compared to pedestrians when navigating a turn. This differentiation reflects the greater deceleration typically required by vehicles to safely maneuver turns, ensuring realistic simulation of movement patterns for both types of users. Finally, we introduce sudden random stops during the pedestrian or vehicle movement. These are determined by a halt probability P_{halt} , that controls whether the velocity at each time step will take the value calculated in (12) or a very small value. Finally, $|v_i(m)|$ is assigned as

$$|v_i(m)_r| = \begin{cases} 0.1, & \text{if } r \leq P_{\text{halt}}, \\ \bar{v}_i \left(\frac{180^\circ - |\theta_t(m)|}{180^\circ} \right)^{d_R}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (13)$$

where once again, $r \in [0, 1]$ is the random factor. For pedestrians, we set $P_{\text{halt}} = 0.05$ while for vehicles it is $P_{\text{halt}} = 0.15$, and it is applied only when the average velocity assigned to the vehicle is low.

Fig. 8. The angle of approach θ_t increases when the new track traces approximate a turn in the predefined path. The sector of movement is determined by the bearing and $\Delta\theta_{\max}$ in terms of direction range and by $v \cdot \Delta t$, which is the movement radius.

Additionally, we need to determine the time interval between the traces of the new track, which depends on the desired frequency for DoA estimation. Given the simplicity of our approach and the demanding computational load from higher DoA estimation frequencies, we set the time interval between steps to $\Delta t = 1\text{sec}$.

Finally, further consideration is needed regarding the avoidance of buildings. The predefined paths designed on sidewalks around buildings are carefully drawn to avoid intersecting them. However, given the random movement of pedestrians, it is possible that a proposed trace $T_i(m)$ lands on coordinates occupied by a building. In such cases, we slowly divert the direction of movement back to the predefined path while still preserving its randomness. To achieve this, we developed a small routine that attempts to avoid buildings by repeatedly calculating a new position until a threshold is reached. At each attempt, the maximum angular deviation sector is decreased until it becomes zero, at which point $T_i(m)$ is directed straight towards $P(k+1)$ of the predefined path. There is also a threshold for the number of attempts after which the track restarts anew. This routine along with a synoptic description of the entire track generation algorithm is described by Algorithm 1. An example of a generated track is also shown in Fig. 9.

E. Ray Tracing Heuristic

Moving on to the collection of DoAs, we employ an efficient technique to take advantage of the ray tracing tool offered by the MATLAB Antenna Toolbox [51]. The ray tracing propagation model computes multiple propagation paths determining phase shift and path loss. The path loss calculations include

Algorithm 1 Track Generation Algorithm

```

while recorded traces < min steps :
  Initialize track
  for steps = 1 to max steps :
    if on_roof_counter == attempt threshold :
      break
    Calculate target point, velocity
    on_building_counter ← 0
    on_building ← True
    while on_building == True :
      Generate trace
      if trace is on a building :
        on_building_counter += 1
        Δθ_max ← Δθ_max - 5°
        if on_roof_counter == attempt threshold :
          break
      else :
        on_building ← False
        Δθ_max ← Initial Δθ_max
    end while
  Save trace
end for
end while

```


Fig. 9. A new track (green) generated based on a predefined path (red).

free-space loss, reflection losses, and diffraction losses. For each reflection and diffraction, the model calculates losses on the horizontal and vertical polarizations by using the Fresnel equation, the uniform theory of diffraction, the geometric angle, and the complex permittivity of the interface materials at the specified frequency. Each ray path calculated by the propagation model is complemented by certain properties which include the direction of departure (DoD) and DoA from the transmitter to a receiver. For the purposes of this study, to identify the DoA for a certain location of a user in the urban area, there needs to be at least one ray that is able to reach the user from the UPA. By increasing the maximum number of reflections and diffractions, we can increase the likelihood of discovering one or multiple paths. However, this comes

with an increase in computational cost. Thereby, we employ a heuristic method that starts by attempting to find LoS paths and if no paths are found, it proceeds by increasing the number of reflections and diffractions according to the priority described in Table I. Higher order classes of propagation paths have been considered (more reflections and diffractions or combinations of them), however no considerable gains in accuracy have been reported. This is perfectly in line with propagation characteristics of mmWave in an urban environment, where the effect of multiple propagation mechanisms is less pronounced compared to lower frequencies. Lastly, we consider concrete to be the material both for terrain and buildings.

TABLE I
RAY-TRACING HEURISTIC

Attempt	Max Reflections	Max Diffractions
1	-	-
2	1	-
3	2	-
4	2	1
5	3	1

III. DATASET PREPARATION

Having configured both the method to produce new trajectories and the ray-tracing model that yields the DoAs for each step of these trajectories, we proceed to produce the dataset needed to train the NNs. We start by generating 1.3×10^5 tracks out of which 9×10^4 are pedestrian tracks and 4×10^4 are vehicle tracks. For each step of each track, we run the ray-tracing propagation model, which, due to multi-path propagation, produces one or more rays connecting the UPA with the user's location at the corresponding step of the track. We then record the DoA of the ray with the lowest path loss. Essentially, we aim to predict the future trajectory of users as perceived by the base station. The NNs will be designed to forecast the next DoA of a moving user by analyzing the rate and direction of angular change between the previously recorded DoAs of this user. Therefore, we plan to input into the NNs the DoA angles, the angular velocity, and angular acceleration observed between each timestep. Considering a scenario where we want to predict the future DoA given the one of the current timestep and N_{obs} past DoAs, it is necessary to observe at least $N_{\text{obs}} + 3$ past steps. That is because calculating the angular velocity at timestep t , requires the DoAs of timesteps t and $t - 1$. Similarly, determining the angular acceleration at timestep t , necessitates the angular velocities of timesteps t and $t - 1$, which in turn requires the DoAs of timesteps t , $t - 1$ and $t - 2$. Thus, depending on the total number of observations needed to predict the future DoA, a minimum track length can be defined.

During the DoA collection process, transitioning from a LoS to a NLoS connection is expected to cause an abnormal angular deviation between consecutive DoAs. In NLoS areas, the optimal paths from scatterers might not display any clear relation to one another, disrupting the more "logical" progression observed in LoS tracks. A primary goal of this study is to investigate whether the NNs can recognize that certain DoAs pertain to NLoS scenarios, necessitating a different prediction

"logic" for future steps. The NN might identify patterns or indicators in the input data correlating to these unique cases, such as sudden changes in angular velocity or signals coming from specific angular sectors. For this purpose, we decided to introduce a binary indicator E_t . This indicator is intended to inform the NN that it is dealing with a peculiar case such as the transition between a LoS to a NLoS scenario. This indicator could be dictated by a variety of measurements, such as the time difference of arrival of a signal or a rapid change in received signal strength. In an attempt to maintain a simplistic approach, we set this indicator to "1" when a velocity or acceleration of extreme value is noticed in a record. As an extreme value, we define the values that lie in the outlier region of the velocity and acceleration distributions. This region can be defined after collecting and analyzing the entire dataset. In addition, we also activate this indicator for the record of the previous timestep so that this feature also functions as a warning that extreme values are expected in future timesteps.

Before training the NNs, it is crucial to normalize the input data [43]. The sign of the velocity value (positive or negative) is necessary for accurately understanding the direction of movement relative to a reference state. Inputs for velocity or acceleration that encompass both positive and negative values convey richer information about the direction of movement compared to solely non-negative inputs. For this purpose, we opt to normalize input to the $[-1, 1]$ sector, rather than $[0, 1]$, ensuring that the directional information, indicated by the sign of the values, is preserved and effectively utilized by the NNs.

We focus on signals arriving at the front side of the UPA, specifically within the angular sectors $[0^\circ, 90^\circ]$ for elevation and $[-180^\circ, 180^\circ]$ for azimuth. Normalizing the DoAs within a $[-1, 1]$ range using these angles directly could mislead the NN due to the lack of continuity between the azimuth angles of 180° and -180° , which are adjacent in reality but would appear as opposites in this scheme. To resolve this, we adopt a different convention just for the training of the NNs.

Fig. 10. The convention followed to transform azimuth and elevation angles. This transformation takes place only before the DoAs enter the NN. It is designed to avoid misinterpreting the bounds of the angular sector as disconnected extremes.

As illustrated in Fig. 10, we transform the DoAs by dividing the azimuth into two quadrants distinguished by the sign of the elevation angle. The first quadrant encompasses the original

azimuth sector $[-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ which is now associated only with positive elevation angles $[0^\circ, 90^\circ]$. The second quadrant combines the remaining parts of the azimuth range, now redefined within the same $[-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ range, associated only with negative elevation angles $[-90^\circ, 0^\circ]$. This redefinition ensures that NNs correctly interpret the continuity between azimuth angles, facilitating a more accurate learning and prediction of DoA trajectories.

The final dataset is comprised of both pedestrian and vehicle movement DoA trajectories. This widens the range of recorded values for both velocity and acceleration. Moreover, as we previously mentioned, there are some cases with extreme outlying values due to NLoS propagation which broadens the spread of values even further. This makes a min-max normalization harder, as most data are concentrated within the $[\mu - 3\sigma, \mu + 3\sigma]$ sector of each feature distribution. In the context of this implementation, outlier values are meaningful for the training of the TNN as they are indicators of NLoS scenarios. With the help of the added feature E_t , we make sure that such records can still be represented even if such outlying values are capped. This enables us to normalize each feature within a smaller range without losing the context an extreme value offers. After performing a statistical analysis on the entire dataset to obtain the mean and standard deviation for the distribution of each feature, we normalize the angular velocities and accelerations within their respective $[\mu - 3\sigma, \mu + 3\sigma]$ range.

A. Sliding Window

When a new track is generated, the maximum and minimum length of the track can be predetermined but the final length of the track can vary. This depends on the velocity of the user, the proximity of the starting point to the end of the predefined path and lastly, the length of the original predefined path. Interestingly, the final dataset consisting of various lengths, can be further exploited for training. The sliding window technique is a fundamental approach for processing sequential data, particularly useful when dealing with datasets of varying lengths. By defining a fixed-size window that slides over the data sequence, this method enables the extraction of localized segments of the sequence at regular intervals. Each window effectively captures a snapshot of temporal information within the specified frame, which helps to standardize input lengths for training NNs. This technique enhances dataset utilization by generating multiple training samples from a single sequence, thereby augmenting the data and improving the robustness of the model.

For our study, we select a window size equal to the number of observations we wish the NN to require in order to predict the future DoA. For TNNs, training with a constant input length does not restrict inference for input sequences of longer or shorter lengths. This is not the case for RNNs, where this fixed window size would dictate the maximum input sequence length. The window size was selected to be equal to 6, trying to balance having a long enough sequence to hold enough information about the trajectory and short enough to present a challenge for the NNs. With the initial number of generated

tracks counting up to 1.3×10^5 , and track lengths ranging between 7 and 50 steps, after applying the sliding window technique we end up with a training set of nearly 2.8×10^6 records. Each record represents a sub-sequence extracted from the generated tracks which has a fixed length of $5 + 1$ steps. The extra step represents the target future DoA which the NNs will be trained to predict. For each record, the fifth step is considered as the current timestep while the previous are the past DoA observations. This defines the number of past observations as $N_{\text{obs}} = 4$.

IV. KALMAN FILTER IMPLEMENTATION

We implement a Kalman filter to predict the future DoAs ϕ_{t+1} (azimuth) and θ_{t+1} (elevation) based on past observations and known motion dynamics. The state vector is defined as:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_t \\ \dot{\phi}_t \\ \theta_t \\ \dot{\theta}_t \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

where ϕ_t and θ_t are the angular positions, and $\dot{\phi}_t$ and $\dot{\theta}_t$ are the angular velocities. Including velocities in the state vector is crucial because it allows the filter to model the dynamic behavior of the user's movement, accounting for the momentum of movement.

Angular accelerations $\ddot{\phi}_t$ and $\ddot{\theta}_t$ are treated as known control inputs and included in the control vector:

$$\mathbf{u}_t = \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{\phi}_t \\ \ddot{\theta}_t \end{bmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

By incorporating accelerations as control inputs rather than state variables, we simplify the model and reduce computational complexity. This approach leverages the known accelerations to influence the state transition directly, improving prediction without increasing the dimensionality of the state.

The state transition equation with control inputs is:

$$\mathbf{x}_{t+1} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}_t + \mathbf{w}_t, \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{F} is the state transition matrix defined as:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \Delta t & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \Delta t \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (17)$$

and \mathbf{B} is the control input matrix:

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2}\Delta t^2 & 0 \\ \Delta t & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2}\Delta t^2 \\ 0 & \Delta t \end{bmatrix}. \quad (18)$$

The process noise \mathbf{w}_t accounts for model uncertainties. The measurement equation is:

$$\mathbf{z}_{t+1} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}_{t+1}, \quad (19)$$

with the measurement matrix \mathbf{H} given by:

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

V. NEURAL NETWORK APPROACHES

A. Transformer Implementation

Let the observed DoA of a user at time t be denoted by $\{\phi_t, \theta_t\}$. We can define the input information for each user, denoted by $X_t = \{\phi_t, \theta_t\}$ and the context $C_t = \{\dot{\phi}_t, \dot{\theta}_t, \ddot{\phi}_t, \ddot{\theta}_t, E_t\}$, where ϕ_t and θ_t are the azimuth and elevation angle, $\dot{\phi}_t$ and $\dot{\theta}_t$ are the azimuth and elevation angular velocities and $\ddot{\phi}_t$ and $\ddot{\theta}_t$ are the azimuth and elevation angular accelerations. The feature E_t is a binary indicator used to convey both the transition between LoS and NLoS parts of a track and the operation within NLoS conditions. We aim to develop a model to predict the future DoA of the user, $\hat{X}_{t+1} = \{\phi_{t+1}, \theta_{t+1}\}$, based on inputs $X_{t-j} = \{\phi_{t-j}, \theta_{t-j}\}$ and context $C = \{\dot{\phi}_{t-j}, \dot{\theta}_{t-j}, \ddot{\phi}_{t-j}, \ddot{\theta}_{t-j}, E_{t-j}\}$ ($j = 0, 1, \dots, N_{\text{obs}}$) where N_{obs} is the number of past observations. Since we are only interested for predicting the future DoA just for the next timestep, we do not require the decoder part of the original TNN architecture [33]. This could be used to predict more than one step into the future of a trajectory.

The inference process is illustrated in Fig. 11. Both input DoAs and their respective context are first passed through an embedding layer to create a higher-dimensional vector representation of this information. The size of the input array is $N_{\text{obs}} + 1 \times 2$, containing the DoAs of $N_{\text{obs}} + 1$ timesteps, while the context array has a size of $N_{\text{obs}} + 1 \times 5$, containing the velocities, accelerations, and the binary NLoS indicator for $N_{\text{obs}} + 1$ timesteps. We then pass each through the positional encoder and concatenate them into a single vector. The role of the positional encoder is to add information about the sequence order of the inputs, which is crucial for the model to understand the temporal relationship between the data points. Next, this information is passed to the encoder architecture, which is comprised of normalization layers, multi-head attention layers, fully connected layers, and residual connections. TNNs use a multi-head self-attention mechanism to capture both short and long-term dependencies within the input sequence. Each attention head computes a weighted relationship between the input DoAs and the added context, allowing the model to focus on key parts of the data. This is particularly important in our work where predicting the future DoA can only be achieved by understanding the movement patterns between the DoAs of different timesteps and the impact of NLoS situations which highly perplexes this prediction. Multiple attention heads further enhance the model by learning various dependencies simultaneously. Finally, we apply another feedforward layer to transform the processed information into a vector of two values (azimuth and elevation of future DoA), followed by a tanh activation function to regulate the output values within the $[-1, 1]$ range. The addition of the tanh activation function at the end helps by ensuring a stable output that aids in faster convergence and better generalization of the model. We decided not to perform hyperparameter tuning on the encoder architecture and to test two variations of this model instead. A small and a big version defined by the total number of

parameters the model is using are trained and tested. The selection of training and design-related hyperparameters is shown in Table II. During training, a learning rate scheduler with a certain patience (as shown in Table II) is applied to decrease the learning rate when a plateau is observed in the validation error [54]. To avoid excess computational time, the training progress is set for an early stop if one of the following conditions are met. Firstly, if learning rate has decreased to the point where it no longer contributes significantly to the training process. Secondly, if overfitting occurs for the 10 most recent epochs. Lastly, training stops if the validation error does not decrease for 20 consecutive epochs. As it is later demonstrated in Section VI-A, increasing the number of parameters of the model does not significantly affect its performance, which validates the initial intuition that hyperparameter optimization can be omitted for this task.

Fig. 11. Transformer (encoder-only) architecture and inference flow. The addition symbol signifies the concatenation of the input vectors.

TABLE II
TNN MODEL HYPERPARAMETERS

Training-Related	Value
Batch Size	64
Learning Rate	1×10^{-4}
Optimizer	Adam
Scheduler Patience	10
Design-Related	Value (small / big)
Encoder Layers	2 / 4
Size of Hidden Embeddings	256 / 512
Attention Heads	4 / 8
Hidden Size of Feedforward Layer	1024 / 2048
Total parameters	$2.4 \times 10^6 / 12.6 \times 10^6$

B. RNN Approach

Similarly, we can approach this problem with both LSTM-based and GRU-based RNNs. The distinction between these two units lies in the number of gates each uses to produce the output. Studies have shown that GRUs can perform comparably to LSTMs but with a faster temporal response due to their simplified structure and fewer operations [21], [44]. The purpose for testing both models is to see how each performs in terms of accuracy and response time for the proactive beamforming scheme, and to determine if the simplified structure of the GRU offers significant advantages over the LSTM in

this specific application. To avoid redundancy, the following paragraphs analyze the LSTM-RNN deployment, which is essentially the same as the GRU-RNN deployment.

In Fig. 12 the setup of the RNN implementation is illustrated, both for a many-to-one (LSTM-MTO) and a many-to-many (LSTM-MTM) approach. With LSTM-MTO, the model is trained to predict the next DoA given an input sequence of fixed length. On the other hand, the LSTM-MTM approach can be trained to produce an output for an input sequence of variable length. The size of the input array for each implementation is $N_{obs} + 1 \times 2$, containing the DoAs of $N_{obs} + 1$ timesteps. Despite the clear functional advantage of the LSTM-MTM, we decided to try both architectures to see whether there is any trade-off between the models especially when it comes to prediction accuracy. Both models are followed by a fully connected layer followed by a tanh activation function at the output. The sole purpose of the fully connected layer is to transform the hidden state size of the LSTM units to the desired output size.

To tune the design related hyperparameters of these models, we used Bayesian optimization (BO) [55] and a small dataset (a subset of the final training dataset) of 2×10^3 records. The use of BO for hyperparameter tuning has been demonstrated in a lot of works [56], [57], [58], [22] and has proven to be a preferred alternative to common tuning methods such as grid search or other optimization techniques. We selected this method motivated by its ability to navigate the search space in a more efficient way than grid-based methods and by its ability to identify optimal parameter configurations in a shorter amount of time. The target is to tune three hyperparameters, the number of hidden layers, the hidden state size and the dropout rate. We set BO to start with 5 random samples in the search space (shown in Table III) and have the optimization run for 30 iterations. Note that the number of layers increments by 1, hidden state size by 16 and dropout by 0.1. Additionally, a 3-fold cross validation is applied to the dataset for each training to further validate the findings for each tuning attempt. The BoTorch framework was utilized to implement BO for this work [59]. In Table III, the training-related and the final design-related hyperparameters proposed by BO for both models are presented.

The primary distinction between the LSTM-MTO and LSTM-MTM models lies in their training and inference processes. For the LSTM-MTO, data utilization mirrors the preparation for the TNN, except that the context vector is omitted. Each input comprises $N_{obs} + 1$ DoA observations, with the output being a two-element vector representing the future DoA. During the model's inference, only the output from the final timestep is retained. This architecture trains the fully connected layer to specifically interpret the final step's output.

In contrast, the LSTM-MTM model accommodates inputs of variable sequence lengths. This flexibility is achieved by randomly masking records to lengths between 1 and $N_{obs} + 1$, and padding the remainder to standardize the dataset size. In this model, the output of each timestep is preserved and processed by the fully connected layer, which is now trained to interpret outputs from multiple, rather than solely the final,

Fig. 12. Up: Many-to-one approach Down: Many-to-Many approach.

timesteps. To ensure the model emphasizes the accuracy of the final timestep output—the prediction of the future DoA—the loss is calculated by comparing only this last non-zero output with the target future DoA. Specifically, if N_b is the number of sequences in a batch, \hat{y}_i the prediction of the model for the last valid timestep of the i -th sequence, and y_i the true DoA at the next timestep, the root mean square error (RMSE) loss function L is defined as follows:

$$L = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_b} \sum_{i=1}^{N_b} (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2} \quad (21)$$

In our experiments, we also tested other loss functions such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) to evaluate their impact on the training process. However, we ultimately chose to work with RMSE due to its several advantages. Due to the squaring operation in RMSE, it provides a more sensitive measure of large errors, which is crucial for predicting DoAs accurately. This is more pronounced in volatile NLoS scenarios where rapid fluctuations between consecutive DoA values can occur, leading to increasingly unbalanced predictions from the models. While MAE treats all errors equally, without allowing outlier values to influence the evaluation, RMSE penalizes larger errors more heavily, thereby encouraging the model to reduce significant deviations. This makes RMSE a better fit for capturing the precise performance of our models in predicting future DoAs.

Both the GRU-MTO and GRU-MTM models have the same configuration as shown in Fig. 12 by replacing the LSTM units with GRUs. To train the GRU models we use the same training-related parameters for the LSTM as shown in Table III. We also perform BO to optimize the design-related hyperparameters of the GRU-RNN implementation, and end up with the tuning described in IV.

VI. RESULTS

In this section, we present a comprehensive performance analysis of the different models implemented in this study. All models have been trained using the hyperparameters and

TABLE III
LSTM MODEL HYPERPARAMETERS

Training-Related		Value
Batch Size		64
Learning Rate		1×10^{-4}
Optimizer		Adam
Scheduler Patience		10
Weight Decay		1×10^{-4}
Design-Related	Search Space	Proposed by BO MTO / MTM
Number of Layers	[1, 4]	3 / 1
Hidden State Size	[128, 1024]	320 / 608
Dropout	[0.0, 0.4]	0.0 / 0.0
Total Parameters	-	2×10^6 / 1.5×10^6

TABLE IV
GRU MODEL HYPERPARAMETERS

Design-Related	Search Space	Proposed by BO MTO / MTM
Number of Layers	[1, 4]	3 / 2
Hidden State Size	[128, 1024]	160 / 160
Dropout	[0.0, 0.4]	0.0 / 0.0
Total Parameters	-	3.8×10^5 / 2.3×10^5

techniques discussed in the previous sections. All model implementations and training were conducted using the PyTorch framework on an NVIDIA A100-SXM4-40GB GPU. We evaluate the variations of each architecture presented and then we perform a comparative analysis between the candidate models. To achieve this, we create a new set of predefined paths that differs from the one used in the generation of the training dataset. In total, 7×10^3 new trajectories were created, out of which 5×10^3 are pedestrian and 2×10^3 are vehicle paths. Upon these new paths we generate the test dataset which after applying the sliding window technique, holds approximately 1.9×10^5 records.

A. TNN Model Performance

To evaluate the contribution of the context vector to the model training, we compare the training performance between the small TNN model trained with and without the context vector. In addition, we observe the training performance of the big TNN model, to evaluate the contribution the additional parameters offer compared to the small TNN model. Training and validation error curves are shown in Fig. 13 below. We implemented multiple termination criteria to optimize the training process, and in all cases, training was stopped early due to stagnant validation error, as depicted by the flat validation loss lines in Fig. 13. The figure is cropped at the point where the latest validation loss plateau starts, which ensures focus on the most critical phase of model training.

It is evident that the added context vector elevates the training performance of the small TNN model as both training and validation error maintain a constant advantage of lower RMSE values compared to the respective "no-context" learning curves, throughout the training duration. Considering this advantage, and the fact that calculating the context vector adds no considerable computational complexity to the model's inference, we disregard the case of a "no-context" TNN implementation. Next, we compare the small and big variations

Fig. 13. Training and validation performance comparison between the variations of the TNN model.

of the TNN model. Evidently, the nearly six-times larger size of the big TNN model does not appear to have a great impact on the training performance of the TNN model as the slightly improved learning curves of the big TNN model are not considerably lower than the small TNN curves, especially when validation loss is observed. Nevertheless, the angular accuracy of each model requires further examination. For this purpose, we perform a statistical analysis of the angular error of their predictions. This error is calculated as the angular divergence between the future DoA predicted by the models and the real future DoA of the sixth timestep. Considering $\phi_{\text{pred}}, \theta_{\text{pred}}$ and $\phi_{\text{real}}, \theta_{\text{real}}$ to be the azimuth and elevation angles of the predicted and real DoA respectively, the angular divergence δ is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta = \cos^{-1} & \left(\sin \theta_{\text{pred}} \cos \phi_{\text{pred}} \sin \theta_{\text{real}} \cos \phi_{\text{real}} \right. \\ & + \sin \theta_{\text{pred}} \sin \phi_{\text{pred}} \sin \theta_{\text{real}} \sin \phi_{\text{real}} \\ & \left. + \cos \theta_{\text{pred}} \cos \theta_{\text{real}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

The boxplots illustrating the distribution of angular divergence for both TNN variations are shown in Fig. 14. We notice a similar performance between these two model variations as the inter-quartile range of both distributions extends between the same values. Both models present excellent accuracy, with the mean angular divergence being less than 2 degrees. This indicates that these models are highly capable, performing adequately in both LoS and NLoS scenarios.

B. LSTM and GRU Models Performance

After training the LSTM-MTO and LSTM-MTM models, we conducted a similar statistical analysis to that performed on the TNN model. Once again the test dataset is used for this analysis, comprised of tracks that these models have no prior experience on. The results are shown in Fig. 15. We first observe that both LSTM implementations demonstrate remarkable accuracy at this task, almost similar to that of the TNN model. The initial intuition that the LSTM-MTO model might perform better for a sequence of a fixed-length is validated here as both the distribution of prediction error

Fig. 14. Boxplots of angular error distribution between the TNN-big and TNN-small model predictions utilizing 5 past observations.

and the mean angular divergence of that model is better than the LSTM-MTM.

Finally, we conduct a statistical analysis for the GRU-based models, with the results presented in Fig. 15. Both models exhibit performance that is nearly identical to the LSTM-based RNNs. Interestingly, the GRU-MTM model seems to be slightly more accurate than its LSTM counterpart despite having significantly less trainable parameters when compared in Tables III and IV. This reinforces their competitiveness in comparison with the other models. However, the final assessment will be determined through a more comprehensive evaluation of their capabilities in the following paragraphs.

Fig. 15. Boxplots of angular error distribution between the LSTM-based and GRU-based model predictions utilizing 5 past observations.

C. Comparison between the NN Types

1) *Time Complexity Analysis:* The time complexity of the TNN model can be analyzed by considering the positional encoding, contextual embedding, and the transformer encoder layers. Let n be the length of the sequence, d be the dimensionality of input features, h be the dimensionality of the

hidden state, L be the number of encoder layers, b be the batch size, m be the dimension of the continuous features, and c be the dimension of the binary features. The positional encoding has a complexity of $O(nh)$. The contextual embedding combines binary and continuous features with a complexity of $O((c+m) \cdot h/2)$. Each transformer encoder layer, consisting of multi-head self-attention and feed-forward networks, has a complexity of $O(nh^2 + n^2h)$. With L encoder layers, the total complexity for the encoder is $O(L(nh^2 + n^2h))$. Including the additional operations for concatenation and final projection, the overall complexity of the model simplifies to $\Theta(Lnh^2)$. This indicates that the computational cost grows quadratically with the hidden dimension and linearly with the sequence length and number of encoder layers.

The time complexity of LSTM-based models, both LSTM-MTO and LSTM-MTM, can be analyzed by considering the operations within each LSTM cell and the additional layers in the models. Let n be the sequence length, d be the input feature dimensionality, h be the hidden state dimensionality, L be the number of layers, and o be the output dimensionality. Each LSTM cell computes four gates (input, forget, cell, and output), involving matrix multiplications with complexities $O(h \cdot d)$ and $O(h \cdot h)$. Thus, the complexity for one timestep in one layer is $O(4hd + 4h^2)$. For a sequence of length n and L hidden layers, the total complexity for the LSTM is $O(nLhd + nLh^2)$. In the LSTM-MTO model, the final linear layer adds a negligible complexity of $O(ho)$ since it is applied only once. In the LSTM-MTM model, the fully connected layer applied to each timestep has a complexity of $O(nho)$. Despite these differences, the dominant term in both models' complexities is nLh^2 , resulting in a simplified overall complexity of $\Theta(nLh^2)$. This indicates that both LSTM models have the same quadratic growth with the hidden dimension and linear growth with the sequence length and number of layers, highlighting the consistent computational cost structure inherent to LSTM architectures.

On the other hand, the time complexity of GRU-based models, can be analyzed similarly to LSTM models, with some differences in the number of gates and operations. The main difference is that a GRU cell computes three gates (update, reset, and candidate). Thus, the complexity for one timestep in one layer is $O(3hd + 3h^2)$. For a sequence of length n and L layers, the total complexity for the GRU layers is $O(nLhd + nLh^2)$. In the GRU-MTO model, the final linear layer adds a negligible complexity of $O(ho)$ since it is applied only once. In the GRU-MTM model, the fully connected layer applied to each timestep has a complexity of $O(nho)$. Once again, despite these differences, the dominant term in both models' complexities is nLh^2 , resulting in a simplified overall complexity of $\Theta(nLh^2)$. This indicates that both GRU models have the same quadratic growth with the hidden dimension and linear growth with the sequence length and number of layers, similar to their LSTM counterparts but with slightly fewer operations per timestep due to fewer gates. Despite LSTMs performing slightly more operations per timestep due to the additional gate, both models share the same time complexity in Big O notation because the quadratic term h^2 dominates for large hidden state dimensions.

2) *Accuracy and Response Time Comparison*: By comparing the results presented in Fig. 14 and Fig. 15, we observe a slight advantage of the TNN models over the LSTM and GRU-based ones. In Table V, we present a comparison of the error for each model, distinguishing between pedestrian and vehicle tracks. In addition, we include the mean inference time for each model. This is measured as the time needed to predict the future DoA given a sequence of $N_{\text{obs}} + 1$ DoAs. To simulate the application on a more lightweight and portable system, we opted to demonstrate the inference time on a smaller GPU than the one used for training. Therefore, the following measurements were made on an Apple M1 Max chip with 32GB LPDDR5 SDRAM. The metal performance shaders (MPS) backend for GPU acceleration are utilized for evaluating these models.

Evidently, there seems to be a trade-off between accuracy and response time. For an approximate degradation of 0.6° in mean prediction accuracy, the LSTM-MTM model seems to be able to provide a future DoA prediction approximately 5 times faster than the TNN models. The GRU-MTM on the other hand is both faster and more accurate than the LSTM making it a better alternative to the TNN models.

As expected, despite the Kalman filter having the lowest response time out of the NN models, it has the highest mean prediction error with high variance, and its degraded performance is more pronounced in vehicle tracks. In addition, we distinguish between LoS and NLoS paths in Table VI. Once again, it becomes apparent why simple techniques like Kalman filters fail to handle more the more demanding NLoS conditions, where there the non-linearity is high and only models with pattern-recognition abilities can derive further meaning by observing the historical DoA data. Therefore, we disregard the Kalman filter as a viable competing solution for this problem. TNNs present the lowest prediction error in NLoS conditions, which further highlights their dominance.

TABLE V
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS ON PEDESTRIAN AND VEHICLE TRACKS

Model	Pedestrian tracks	Vehicle tracks	Response Time (msec)
	prediction error (degrees) Mean / Std	prediction error (degrees) Mean / Std	
Kalman Filter	2.79 / 11.07	4.71 / 13.23	0.11
TNN-small	1.28 / 2.41	2.09 / 3.11	3.0
TNN-big	1.24 / 2.36	1.99 / 2.69	3.4
LSTM-MTO	1.51 / 2.56	2.48 / 3.22	0.66
GRU-MTO	1.58 / 2.50	2.54 / 3.18	0.55
LSTM-MTM	1.81 / 2.24	2.69 / 2.93	0.62
GRU-MTM	1.71 / 2.27	2.61 / 2.89	0.52

The superior performance of TNNs over LSTMs and GRUs is primarily due to the self-attention mechanism, which captures both short and long-term dependencies simultaneously by assigning dynamic weights to all input positions, unlike the sequential processing of LSTMs and GRUs. The inclusion of a context vector that integrates supplementary information and whether the scenario is LoS or NLoS, allows TNNs to adapt predictions more effectively, particularly in challenging NLoS environments where prediction errors are more pronounced (see Table VI).

TABLE VI
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS ON LoS AND NLoS SCENARIOS

Model	LoS	NLoS
	prediction error (degrees) Mean / Std	prediction error (degrees) Mean / Std
Kalman Filter	1.50 / 4.45	21.6 / 33.23
TNN-small	1.42 / 2.35	3.09 / 4.35
TNN-big	1.36 / 2.17	3.01 / 4.12
LSTM-MTO	1.59 / 2.41	4.51 / 4.71
GRU-MTO	1.69 / 2.46	4.38 / 4.41
LSTM-MTM	1.86 / 2.01	4.65 / 4.62
GRU-MTM	1.74 / 2.02	4.79 / 4.72

This brings us to the final comparison. In Fig. 16, we present the mean angular divergence for a different number of input sequence lengths. The models compared here are the ones able to process an input of variable length, that is why the LSTM-MTO and GRU-MTO are not included in the comparison. This figure reveals something that was not be apparent when the two variations of the TNN model were previously compared. That is the ability of the big TNN model to maintain a lower prediction error even when fewer DoAs are used as input. The mean angular divergence shown in the boxplots of Fig. 14 for a sequence length of 5 DoAs, is an attribute that only the big model is able to maintain for shorter input lengths, while the small model's accuracy decreases with fewer DoA observations. Similarly, the LSTM and GRU-MTM models are able to preserve their prediction error for most of the length variations we examined, proving that it can also be a robust solution to the problem in hand. The results of this figure confirm once more that the GRU-MTM model achieves and maintains a better performance to the LSTM-MTM model. Additionally, considering all previous comparisons, the big TNN model seems to prevail in accuracy and proves to have an astonishing performance even with smaller input sequence lengths. Nevertheless, if a slight accuracy degradation can be afforded, the GRU-MTM model seems more suitable for fast-changing scenarios since it has the lowest response time between the models. Finally, since TNNs process inputs in parallel, their response time remains unaffected by sequence length, unlike LSTM-MTM and GRU-MTM, where response time increases with longer sequences. Specifically, the average response time for LSTM-MTM rises from 0.26 ms to 0.62 ms, and for GRU-MTM from 0.19 ms to 0.52 ms, as sequence length increases from 1 to 5 timesteps. Next, we will attempt to test this hypothesis by employing these models on a proactive beamforming scenario.

D. Example on a Random Beamforming Scenario

In the following example we intend to demonstrate a possible operation of the scheme presented in Fig. 2. Specifically, for the NN-beamformer indicated in the proposed proactive system, we use the NN presented in [22]. This model is capable of performing accurate zero-forcing beamforming in three dimensions, for a different number of incoming SoAs. The RNN-zero-forcing model (RNN-ZF) is trained to produce the weight vector after receiving a sequence of DoAs as input, considering the first one to be the DoA of SoI and the

Fig. 16. Comparison of mean angular prediction error between the models for a different number of observations.

subsequent ones the DoAs of SoAs. In the following scenario we choose to work on the simple scenario of 3 incoming signals with one SoI and two SoAs. We randomly select three tracks out of those in the test dataset ensuring that each track represented a different activity type. This allows for a more comprehensive evaluation of each model's robustness across users with varying movement speeds. These tracks are illustrated in Fig. 17. For a three-dimensional representation, Fig. 18 illustrates the location of the moving users every two timesteps and the LoS rays that connect the base station with each user. We opted not to include the NLoS rays to keep the illustration less confusing.

Fig. 17. User routes and location of the base station.

The simulation begins with updating the geographical coordinates of each user at each timestep. Once a sufficient number of DoAs (at least 5+2 as described in Section III) have been collected, we can start utilizing the trained models. At each timestep, the DoAs predicted by the models, based on the past five observations, are extracted alongside the "real DoA" of the ray with the lowest path loss identified by the ray-tracing tool. We store the angular error between the predicted and the

Fig. 18. Three-dimensional representation of moving users and the adaptive beamforming process. The red and black figures represent the interference users while the blue figure represents the desired user.

real DoAs for each of the three tracks, which we later present in Fig. 19.

It is crucial to note that the inference of the DoA-predictive models can be performed in batch mode. This means the models can provide the future DoA for each of the three user trajectories simultaneously, incurring the same temporal cost as predicting for a single user.

After gathering the three real DoAs (SoI + 2 SoAs) and the predicted ones, we employ the RNN-ZF model to generate the beamforming weight vector for each DoA combination. Subsequently, we measure the signal strength towards both desired and undesired users based on the radiation pattern produced by each DoA combination. This allows us to monitor the signal-to-interference ratio (SIR) and the fluctuation of the received power of the desired user over time. For comparative purposes, we also include a simple beam-steering method using the real DoAs of the desired user to calculate the steering vector for each direction. By comparing the performance of the AI-based beamformers with the traditional steering vector approach, we can demonstrate the accuracy of this scheme in beam-steering, by observing the received power of the desired user, and the effectiveness of zero-forcing, by observing the SIR. Both aspects are directly correlated to the accuracy of the DoA-prediction models and the RNN-ZF model. These results are shown in Fig. 21 and Fig. 20.

The TNN models exhibit the best performance, consistently maintaining the highest accuracy throughout the timestep progression of each track. The LSTM and GRU-MTO models show some divergence from the DoA trajectory of the SoI for a certain part of the track, but they manage to realign with the rest of the models within 5 timesteps. The transition to a NLoS connection clearly disrupts the predictive ability of the models, as indicated by the second SoA track in Fig. 19. However, the TNN models excel at overcoming this issue, resuming their robust performance within 3 timesteps, whereas the MTO and MTM models take 5 and 7 timesteps, respectively, to recover

Fig. 19. Comparison of DoA prediction error over the timesteps of each user's movement. The dashed horizontal line indicates an angular divergence of 2 degrees. The predictive models are utilized after enough DoAs are collected, indicated by the dashed vertical line. The timesteps during which a user is in NLoS with the base station are indicated with a blue background.

from the NLoS disturbance. Despite processing all inputs in parallel, the NLoS transition on the second SoA track does not affect the accuracy of the SoI and first SoA trajectories, highlighting the models' ability to process each input sequence independently. It is also noteworthy that TNN models consistently exhibit superior performance across all three tracks with varying movement speeds, reinforcing the intuition that incorporating the additional context vector enables TNNs to better capture the dynamic nature of user movement. Among the models, the LSTM-MTM demonstrates the least accuracy, maintaining the highest prediction error, while the big TNN model achieves the lowest prediction error.

The angular precision of each model is also reflected on the signal strength of the desired user in Fig. 20. Once again, the TNN models provide the best performance maintaining the highest signal strength over the major course of the track with the GRU-MTM having a similar performance especially in the early parts. Similarly, the SIR levels of the TNN models in Fig. 21 are the highest for most timesteps following the trend of the RNN-ZF model using the real DoAs. Due to NLoS conditions, there are inconsistencies in some parts of the SIR progression where the performance of the RNN-ZF model with predicted DoAs surpasses that with real DoAs. Because of multi-path propagation, the ray-tracing model identifies multiple rays that connect the receiver (in this case, the undesired user) and the base station. Our proactive models are trained to predict the DoA of the strongest ray with the lowest path loss. However, especially in NLoS conditions, misaligned DoA estimations of the models, might cause slightly inaccurate zero-forcing. This misalignment may inadvertently result in more optimal signal rejection, not by precisely blocking the strongest path, but by rejecting a greater number of scatterers. Consequently, this enhances interference rejection and improves SIR values. This misalignment can have both favorable and unfavorable effects, as indicated by the fluctuations of the models around the performance of the RNN-ZF model with the real DoAs (depicted by the red line in Fig. 21).

After examining the statistical analysis in Section VI-C and the indicative performance of the models in the previous

Fig. 20. Received power of desired user comparison. The predictive models are utilized after enough DoAs are collected, indicated by the dashed vertical line.

example, we conclude that the TNN models are more reliable in the task of future DoA prediction. Despite the GRU models having the fastest response, their slightly degraded accuracy proves to be a serious consideration when it comes to user signal strength and overall SIR. For a sequence length of 5 timesteps, the TNN models have proven to be a robust and reliable solution for this proactive scheme. Out of the two variations, we propose the small TNN model simply for its slightly faster temporal response.

When measuring the mean inference temporal cost of the RNN-NS model (using the same M1-Max processor as in previous measurements) we get a response time of 2.68×10^{-3} seconds. Going back to (1), and considering $t_{BF} = 2.68 \times 10^{-3}$ and $t_{pred} = 3 \times 10^{-3}$, the condition that would enable this

Fig. 21. Comparison of SIR along the timesteps of the movement of users. The predictive models are utilized after enough DoAs are collected, indicated by the dashed vertical line. We classify as NLoS conditions the timesteps where at least one of the users is in NLoS with the base station.

proactive scheme on an Apple M1 Max chip, becomes

$$t_s \geq 5.68 \times 10^{-3} \text{ seconds} \quad (23)$$

This corresponds to a DoA update rate of 176 Hz. This frequency may limit the system's applicability in scenarios requiring higher update rates, such as tracking UAVs or high-speed trains. On the other hand, when employing a more lightweight model like the GRU-MTM, (1) yields $t_s = 3.2 \times 10^{-3}$ seconds, raising the update rate upper bound to 312 Hz, if a degradation in prediction accuracy can be tolerated.

Nevertheless, it is important to note that these estimates are based on tests conducted on an Apple M1-Max processor with 32GB of RAM. With more modern and powerful processors, the response time of the NN models could be significantly reduced, allowing the system to handle applications that demand even higher DoA update rates. This highlights the potential scalability and future applicability of our approach as computing technologies continue to advance.

Depending on the confidence in the accuracy of the predictive models, the frequency of DoA estimation can be reduced. Based on past observations, the predictive models can forecast DoAs for multiple future timesteps, thereby decreasing the need for frequent DoA estimations. This approach can reduce resource consumption and further improve the overall latency of the beamforming process.

While the experimental results focus on smaller-scale systems, the proposed framework is designed to extend to larger, more densely populated environments. The use of TNNs enables parallel processing and the efficient handling of multiple users simultaneously, without sacrificing accuracy or temporal response. This is particularly advantageous in crowded urban

settings. Moreover, the model's ability to handle diverse user speeds and trajectories, as demonstrated in the results of the statistical analysis on 5×10^4 different cases (see Tables V and VI) and the stochastic beamforming scenario, suggests that it can effectively manage varying movement behavior patterns. Future work will further validate the model's scalability by incorporating additional scenarios involving denser populations.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study explores the concept of three-dimensional proactive beamforming using neural networks (NNs). The proposed scheme aims to reduce beamforming latency by transferring the weight calculation process before DoA estimation. An NN-based model predicts future DoAs based on past observations, allowing the system to prepare the weight vector proactively, with the subsequent DoA estimation verifying the accuracy of the prediction. To validate this approach, we simulated an urban environment using OpenStreetMap data, generating realistic pedestrian and vehicle movement paths incorporating both line-of-sight (LoS) and non-line-of-sight (NLoS) conditions to challenge the predictive capabilities of the models. These datasets provided a comprehensive basis for training and testing our models.

After running a statistical analysis on the angular precision of the predictive models, we confirm that transformer neural networks (TNNs), offer superior accuracy and reliability in predicting future DoAs compared to long short-term memory networks (LSTMs) and gated-recurrent units (GRUs) using either the many-to-one or the many-to-many architecture. This comes at the disadvantage of a lower temporal response which is an advantage of the LSTM and GRU models. Additionally, the NN models demonstrate superior performance over the Kalman filter, particularly in NLoS conditions, highlighting why traditional prediction methods are less suited for such a complex task. After testing on a random beamforming scenario with moving users, we validate their predictive capabilities as they showcase optimal signal strength and SIR levels throughout the movement progression. These results illustrate and further substantiate the potential of an end-to-end AI based beamforming system with proactive weight production.

This research exhibits the effectiveness of using TNNs for proactive beamforming, highlighting their capability to manage the complex and dynamic nature of urban wireless communication. The findings pave the way for more adaptive and efficient communication systems in next-generation wireless networks, emphasizing the promising role of AI in future wireless communication technologies. Future work could explore the integration of additional contextual information to further enhance prediction accuracy and system performance. Additionally, optimizing the NN architectures and exploring real-world deployment scenarios will be critical steps toward practical implementation.

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